

COTTON CLEANING MACHINES AND EQUIPMENT

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<https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.7214155>

Abstract

Cotton gin engineering is a branch of heavy machinery that supplies the cotton gin industry with machinery and equipment. This article presents the production program of cotton ginning machines, equipment and cotton ginning machines.

Keywords. Cotton, cotton ginning machines, light industry, textiles, cotton ginning factories.

Аннотация

Хлопкоочистительное машиностроение — отрасль тяжелого машиностроения, снабжающая хлопкоочистительную промышленность машинами и оборудованием. В данной статье представлена производственная программа хлопкоочистительных машин, оборудования и хлопкоочистительных машин.

Ключевые слова. Хлопок, хлопкоочистительные машины, легкая промышленность, текстиль, хлопкоочистительные заводы.

INTRODUCTION

Appropriate programs for the further development of the light industry network are being developed in our country by introducing deep processing of cotton fiber. In particular, 77 important projects with a total value of nearly one billion dollars of the textile industry were implemented on the basis of the program of structural change, modernization and diversification of production adopted in our country in 2015-2019. In recent years, great importance has been attached to the development of light industry. In particular, in order to further develop the industry, 140 projects with a total value of more than 2.2 billion dollars were implemented in the textile and knitting industry in 2017-2021. Special attention is paid to expanding the export of products of light industrial enterprises.

Cotton gin engineering is a branch of heavy machinery that supplies the cotton gin industry with machinery and equipment. Technological devices for cotton processing plants, cotton ginning plants (machines and mechanisms used in cotton preparation, drying, cleaning, storage), saw and roller gin machines, linters, fiber cleaners, seed sorting and cleaning machines, conveyors, produces

cotton gins, cotton conveyors, tunneling machines, cotton gins ventilation and dust collection machines, as well as hemp processing machines and devices (more than 50 names of products in total).

Machine-building enterprises of the cotton ginning industry in Uzbekistan are concentrated in the Association of Machine-Building Enterprises of Uzbekistan - "Uzmashsanoat". The network includes "Uzpaxtamash" joint-stock company (former Tashkent machine-building plant, 1947), Andijan "Tojmetall" joint-stock company (1970), Samarkand "Paxtamash" (1956) and Kattakorgon "Paxtamash" joint-stock companies (1939; 1966). specializing in the production of cotton ginning equipment since 1974), there is the "Olmospaxtamash" joint-stock company in Chust (1974), the cotton-ginning equipment design bureau of the Tashkent "Paxtajin KB" joint-stock company (1953).

Calculation of the production program of cotton ginning enterprises:

Volume of the raw material base, tons	$Q_x = 27000$
The number of equipment producing the main product, pcs	$K_m = 2$
Planned fiber output from seeded cotton, %	$V_v = 30,8$
The order of operation of the enterprise, shift	$N = 3$
Working time of the enterprise in a shift, hours	$t_c = 8,0$
Coefficient of total useful operating time of equipment	$\eta = 0,95$
Lint level, (according to A-type)	$S_{l1} = 2,2$
Lint level, (by B-type)	$S_{l2} = 1,8$
Productivity of the equipment for 1-lint extraction, kg/mash. hour	$P_1 = 1100$
Productivity of the equipment for 2-lint extraction, kg/mash. hour	$P_2 = 950$
The working time fund of cotton ginning enterprises during the year is determined:	

$$T = [N - (N_d + N_b + N_{kt.})] \cdot t_s \cdot N_s \cdot \eta = (248 - (63 + 6 + 30)) \cdot 3 \cdot 8 \cdot 0,95 = 3397.2 \text{ hours}$$

Where: $N = 248$, number of days in a year, day,

N_d = number of days off in 63 years, day

N_b = number of holidays in 6 years, day,

$N_{kt.}$ - the number of days allocated for capital repair of equipment at the cotton ginning enterprise, (unplanned) day

$t_s = 8$, working hours, hours,

$N_s = 3$, operating procedure of the enterprise, shift,

$\eta = 0,95$, useful operating time coefficient of equipment,

CONCLUSION

Manufactured machines and mechanisms are exported to growing countries in the CIS and several foreign countries. The largest enterprise in the network "Uzpxtamash" joint stock company (Tashkent machine-building plant) was launched in 1947. Since 1951, it has specialized in the production of technological equipment and spare parts for the cotton ginning industry ("Toshpaxtamash2"). The enterprise received the name "Uzpxtamash" in 2002. In 1978, cotton processing lines were produced in Uzbekistan and introduced in the cotton ginning industry. "Mehnat" and RX-1 fiber cleaning machines were awarded the gold medal of international fairs in Zagreb (1977), Plovdiv (1979).

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